

PRIORITY DIRECTIONS OF INFORMATION POLICY IN THE CONTEXT OF DISINFORMATION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14890944>

Abstract

This study analyzes the nature and conceptual foundations of false information in the context of globalization, the priority directions of information policy under conditions of disinformation, and the analysis of advanced foreign experiences.

Keywords: state, message, information society, false information, disinformation, information policy, "fake news," globalization.

In today's era, often referred to as the "Information Age," various methods of influencing human consciousness and emotions have emerged. Alongside shaping and developing public opinion through information, information attacks have become a dominant force. "In an information society, new forms of mass communication emerge, leading to transformations in social relations, lifestyles, ways of thinking, and new paradigms in economics, politics, and governance, which necessitate continuous adaptation" [1].

Focusing on the essence of the concepts of the Information Age and the Information Society, we can assert that the Information Age is a period in which the role of information has become central to everyday human activity. In addition to telecommunications tools, mass communication devices (such as telephones, fax machines, and mobile phones) have gained prominence.

In an information society, educational and moral factors become dominant through the use of information tools. "An information society is one in which knowledge and information take a leading role in productive forces, production relations, and capital growth" [2]. Another definition states: "An information society is a society in which sufficient conditions have been created for the preparation, processing, storage, and dissemination of information, playing a primary role in socio-economic development" [3].

As the foundations of the information society—recognized as the third wave of civilization—continue to form, ensuring the dominance of national values guarantees stable development. Conversely, an information society that does not rely on national values gradually loses its ethical foundations under the influence of mass culture, which is a destructive phenomenon. Scholar Rahmon Qo'chqor highlights this issue: 'In today's so-called 'Information World' or

‘Information Society,’ the more mass media disseminates information about an event (regardless of whether it occurred in the past or just yesterday), the more obscure the true reality of that event becomes” [4].

The state's information policy is defined as “a unique type of human activity related to the collection, processing, and dissemination of information, which reflects the interests of the state and civil society while ensuring creative and constructive communication between them and their representatives” [5].

The objects of state information policy include print media—newspapers, magazines, and books—electronic media such as television, radio, and the Internet, as well as communication tools like telephones and pagers. “Information policy can be viewed as a tool of political influence and a means of achieving political goals: through information, the subjects of information policy can influence people's consciousness, psychology, morality, and activities within the framework of state, civil society, and personal interests” [6].

In the struggle for human minds and hearts, the concept of information policy is generally interpreted as the means by which various institutional actors (such as the state, governmental bodies, or individual organizations) interact with existing information flows and resources in accordance with their perspectives and interests [7].

We believe that information policy is an activity aimed at ensuring the stability of national interests through information resources and countering factors that threaten national security while coordinating relations between government institutions and members of society.

Key aspects of globalization include the impact of information, information warfare, ideological and cultural expansion by hegemonic states, and the intensified promotion of lifestyle differences between Western societies, which possess economic dominance, and Eastern nations striving for progress. As a result, globalization is increasingly seen as an era of struggle for human consciousness and emotions.

Today, information tools have become a strategic means of achieving dominance over people. Scholars now define "information influence" as the process of transmitting, processing, creating, and receiving information for the purpose of targeting human consciousness and emotions using specific information weapons [8].

Indeed, effective information influence involves creating and disseminating targeted information to shape human behavior, identity, morality, and psychology, as well as to influence the spiritual and psychological environment

of society and steer public opinion in either a positive or negative direction. The historical development of humanity has led to the emergence of highly effective methods of information influence. As information has taken a leading role, it has also generated information conflicts, which have become a subject of academic research.

According to A. Erkayev: “The emergence of mass communication tools—radio, cinema (and later television, the Internet, and others)—along with mass-produced cultural products such as comics, entertainment works, and vinyl records (later replaced by video and audio discs), has led to the standardization of both material and cultural products. Cultural and spiritual goods have become consumer commodities, losing their local, regional, and national characteristics” [9].

In the field of information conflicts, Russian expert and Doctor of Technical Sciences S. P. Rastorguev defines information warfare as “a targeted information impact in the material sphere, conducted openly or covertly, to achieve a particular advantage through information systems” [10].

He argues that one side gains the upper hand when the opposing side is preoccupied with mitigating the inflicted damage. Rastorguev asserts that, in its nature and characteristics, information warfare is no different from conventional warfare. The aggressor targets all of the adversary's management systems with information influence, subjugating them and achieving victory [11].

According to Rastorguev, there are also effective ways to organize defense against information attacks, including reducing the scale of existing threats, gradually eliminating "unnecessary information," and maintaining strict control over one's own management system. The scholar emphasizes that the strategy of using information weapons must always be forward-looking. He considers this an extremely important but often misunderstood aspect in scientific discourse, as it defines the advancing nature of information weapons and helps assess the capabilities of any strong opponent.

Thus, it can be concluded that the amount of targeted information transmitted from one state to another serves as a measure of information aggression.

The Importance of an Effective Information Policy: Lessons from Developed Countries

Recognizing that implementing an effective information policy is a crucial task in our country today, it is essential to explore various approaches and

choose the most optimal one. Studying the experiences of developed countries can help improve the efficiency of this process.

Focusing on Germany's information policy and its achievements, it is noteworthy that the country's main television and radio channels operate under the jurisdiction of federal states. Germany carries out large-scale activities to protect national interests and enhance its international reputation.

For instance, the "Deutsche Welle" (DW) broadcasting station, established in 1960, can be considered a direct promoter of the country's domestic and foreign policy. "Deutsche Welle" is entirely funded by the federal government. The station's primary broadcast region is the African continent, while its main audiences are in Southern and Eastern Europe, Asia, the Near and Middle East, and Latin America. Interestingly, DW broadcasts very little content to North American countries. The station justifies this by emphasizing the need to provide information to regions with strong censorship and limited press freedom. In contrast, countries where freedom of information and media access are already well-established, such as Austria, do not require such interventions.

In Austria, the political and media spheres are deeply interconnected. This situation is characterized by the composition of the country's political elite and the limited number of political parties and media outlets. Moreover, it is required that their social influence does not become disproportionately dominant.

Most newspapers in Austria strive to cover political forces (political parties) impartially, ensuring they do not earn the reputation of being mere "propaganda tools" for any specific political entity. The relationship between media and political decision-making is becoming increasingly intertwined, sometimes even merging. Many political party activities are now aimed at ensuring their outcomes are swiftly and effectively covered by the media. The increasing professionalism of media engagement is particularly evident in the preparation and execution of election campaigns, where techniques and strategies are often borrowed directly from commercial advertising.

Austrian television is currently transitioning from the state-controlled ORF monopoly to a competitive system with the emergence of private TV channels. There have been extensive debates regarding the potential privatization of ORF. At present, the state broadcaster is funded by viewer-paid fees, advertising revenue, and other legally specified sources of income. ORF is responsible for ensuring the quality of its programming, which includes the dissemination of comprehensive information about the country's political, economic, and cultural

developments, as well as strengthening Austrians' democratic and national identity.

In France, national television and radio broadcasting remained under state monopoly for a long time. Even after the ORTF (French Radio and Television Broadcasting Office) was divided into seven independent companies in 1974, the situation remained largely unchanged. The state monopoly was partially lifted by the law of July 29, 1982. From that moment, changes in the French television system were closely linked to political transformations and ideological shifts, particularly reflecting the balance between the state and the private sector.

In response to the privatization of the TF-1 network by right-wing liberals, left-wing political forces introduced joint management of the France Télévisions company to counterbalance TF-1's growing influence. By the early 1990s, a unique system emerged in France's information policy, in which both the public and private sectors, as well as liberal and authoritarian approaches, coexisted. Although this system was not necessarily the result of an ideal evolutionary process, it clearly reflected the government's consistent oversight of audiovisual media.

In 1985, the French President signed a decree on the creation of private television channels, bringing the audiovisual media sector under the government's indirect but firm control. As a result, throughout all stages of electronic media development, the French state has systematically regulated their political, economic, and technological directions.

The Information Policy of the United Kingdom: Key Features

The information policy of the United Kingdom has its own distinct characteristics. In 1932, BBC radio broadcasts were extended to foreign countries. Initially, they were only conducted in English and targeted British Empire countries such as Australia, India, South Africa, West African nations, and Canada. This service was named the "**BBC Empire Service**" and was financially supported by the Foreign Office. Its primary goal was to promote the ideological values of the British way of life among the population.

For its time, this was a highly innovative approach to shortwave information transmission. Researchers note that the "Empire Service" quickly managed to attract a wide audience across various countries. In 1938, the broadcasts were expanded to Arab countries (the "**Arabic Service**") and Latin American countries (the "**Latin American Service**").

In 1988, BBC leadership implemented a new strategy aimed at improving journalists' professional skills and ensuring their ability to replace one another

when necessary. This strategy ultimately envisioned the complete integration of television and radio broadcasting. At the same time, foreign bureaus were expanded, and new departments with dedicated correspondents were established.

Currently, the BBC broadcasts in approximately **60 languages worldwide**, including in **Central Asia**, where it has regional branches. Notably, the BBC also conducts **broadcasts in Uzbek**.

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